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Religious Hegemony versus Freewill: A Critical Analysis of *Samskara*

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Abstract:

This research paper explores how religious hegemony governs the lives of Brahmins in the villages of Karnataka during the 1960s by giving prominence to patriarchy and by investing unshakable faith in one Acharya, who is supposed to have the knowledge and wisdom of all Hindu scriptures. It reveals how such dependence of society on some Acharyas makes them handicapped, and decays their common sense and rationality while bringing up superstitions and blind faith; all condition the individuals as poor decision makers or unable to make decisions at all during crucial moments of life and death. This paper reveals how people with free will exercise common sense irrespective of their low caste. If a Brahmin does something using his freewill he becomes a villain, and (d)evil in that socio-cultural milieu. Besides, this paper brings out the hypocrisy, duality, and lust of Brahmanical characters, which is worse even than an anti-Brahmanical brahmin. Moreover, this paper showcases how freewill results from the clarity of heart that helps in decision-making for the larger welfare of society. In contrast, religious hegemony prevents an individual from empathizing with others while giving way to hypocrisy.

Keywords: Religious hegemony, wisdom, Hindu scriptures, superstitions, freewill, hypocrisy, socio-cultural milieu.

The novel *Samskara* (1976) opens in Agarhara, a village of Brahmins with Praneshacharya's routine of serving his ailed wife and in the meantime Chandri, the concubine

of Naranappa informs Praneshacharya about Naranappa's demise. Praneshacharya is known as the 'Crest-Jewel of Vedic Learning' (p. 17) or can say the fate of the community whereas Naranappa has brought only disgrace to the community by defying Hinduism and indulging himself in consuming non-vegetarian food and preferring low-caste women for physical gratification. His death becomes the biggest dilemma for the Brahmin community as he has no offspring. After hearing this news all the Brahmins of the village reach Praneshacharya, their guru's home to find out who will cremate the body, but Praneshacharya does not find a way out to this and suggests them to visit Prajatipura where low-caste Brahmins live and thereafter the preacher in monastery. At both places, they do not get an answer for four nights and still depend on Praneshacharya. During this period of visit, Dasacharya dies of fever and others too experience high fever whereas Praneshacharya's wife dies when there is no one in the village except him. It is altogether a different matter that Chandri had cremated the body during the second night which Brahmins of the village are not aware of except Praneshacharya who too knows via Putta.

Suruchi Sharma (pp. 28-33), Shwet Nisha (pp. 30-36), and Gladin Rose (pp. 190-196) bring out the hypocrisy prevalent in Brahminical patriarchal society, Abhinanda Roy (pp. 45-51) and Marasinghe (pp. 168-178) dwell on casteism and social exclusion, Milan Swaroop Sharma (pp. 185-194) and Rajesh Shrinivas Shesham (pp.1-5) discuss rituals in conflict with modernization, S. Chitra (pp. 23-30) and Sanjeev Kumar Sharma depict emptiness of cultural hegemony, Bodhale (pp. 584-594) and Sharon Pillai (pp. 97-119) speak on moral degeneration, whereas Arijit Mondal (pp.193-203) and Sanjeev Kumar Sharma (pp. 112-126) discuss Superstitions an integral part of Indian cultural setup. Besides these, Rupal S. Patel presents the irony of Indian society through satire (pp. 1-4).

The Italian thinker, Antonio Gramsci (1891-1934) popularized the term "Hegemony". He contrasts rule which is direct political control, which uses force whenever it is necessary whereas hegemony functions through the circulation of ideology not as a visible force but as a more subtle, invisible, and unconscious suggestion. For this, Ideology requires a commonly accepted cultural structure like popular culture, folk songs, legends, and local myths through which it becomes an integral part of the lives of people in society (Bary 158). Further, through hegemony "a social class achieves a predominant influence and power not by direct and overt means but by

succeeding in making its ideological views so pervasive that the subordinate classes unwittingly accept and participate in their oppression" (Abrahms 208) deliberating on hegemony, Pramod K. Nayar says that hegemony is the domination of particular section of society like the powerful classes not essentially through intimidation of violence or the law but by winning their consent for getting governed and dominated. Like ideology, it works through consent rather than force (Nayar 130). In this way, hegemony is achieved through the circulation of ideology. Ideology has been a very key term for Louis Althusser who has defined "Ideology is a system (possessing its logic and proper rigour) of representations (images, myths, ideas or concepts according to the case) endowed with an existence and a historical role at the heart of a given society" (Bary 157). Through his essay "Ideology and Ideological State Apparatuses" Althusser says that to bring desirable changes in the society, society or state uses either repressive structures or forces i.e. police force, army, prison, law courts, etc. or ideological structures like schools, churches, family, art, media literature and so on. If the repressive structures use power or force, the latter wins the consent of the masses, which becomes hegemony (Bary 157-58). Raymond Williams defines hegemony as "the whole lives social process as practically organized by specific and dominant meanings, values and beliefs, of a kind which can be abstracted as 'world view' or 'class outlook'" (Williams 101). Mechanics of ideology that serve hegemonic purposes, work through six different strategies according to Terry Eagleton: by promoting beliefs and values congenial to it; naturalizing these beliefs to render them self-evident; universalizing these beliefs; devaluing ideas that might challenge them; rejecting alternative or rival forms of thought; obscuring social reality (Nayar 132). Therefore, based on the theories propounded by these theorists, hegemony becomes a process that contains ideology through which the dominant classes maintain power over the dominated class by winning their consent. Hegemony functions most effectively when the dominated accept their domination due to faith or ideological programming.

Mythology plays a vital role in universalizing hegemony in a particular culture. As per the Glossary of Literary Terms, mythology is a system of hereditary stories of ancient origin that were once believed to be true by a particular cultural faction, and which served to explain the intentions and manners of the deities and other supernatural beings why the world is, as it is and why the things happen as they do, to provide reasons and justification for social customs, observances, and to establish the sanctions for the conventions or norms by which people drive

their lives. Most myths are related to social rituals like set forms and procedures in sacred ceremonies. In Classical Greek myth is known as "mythos" which stands for any story or plot whether true or invented (Abrahms 230). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* describes mythology as the "ideas that many people think are true but that do not exist or are false: the popular mythology that life begins at forty" (Turnbull 1012). Whereas, *the Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory* describes myth as an ancient story that is about gods and their mysterious activities. There may be human characters in myths but the main characters must be supernatural beings. Collectively myths are called mythology. Greek mythology, Roman mythology, Egyptian mythology, and Indian mythologies are well-known examples of mythology in this world (Cuddon 526).

The novelist presents the hegemonic structure of society through the dilemma of cremation after Naranappa's death. As Chandri, Naranappa's concubine runs to Praneshcharya's home and calls Acharya while shivering from the courtyard as he comes out she says while sobbing that Naranappa died due to a four-day fever. Praneshacharya immediately runs to Garudacharya and Garudacharya to Lakshmanacharya and then informs all the Brahmins of Agarhara (pp. 2-3). Immediately after the news, the men move to Acharya's home, and their wives warn their husbands, "Don't be in a hurry. Wait till Praneshacharya gives you a decision. Don't agree too quickly to perform the rites. You may do the wrong thing. The guru may excommunicate you" (p. 4). As they gather, Acharya says that doing Naranappa's death rites is a problem as he has no son. He says that the Holy scriptures mention that in this case, any relative can perform and in the absence of relatives, any Brahmin can perform the death rites. (p. 5) To reach some decision, Praneshacharya tells them to send someone to Prajatipura with this news if they wish to perform the rites and advises them to go home as he will read Manu Smriti and other holy texts (p. 14). He also tells them that no one can eat and cook until the cremation is done, though children can eat at home. When Shankarayya, the priest of Prajatipura understood the issue as Naranappa had drunk liquor, eaten meat, lived with a low-caste woman, and thrown stones into the Holy river or did anti-Brahminical things, he said, "If that's so, wait, we can't do anything rash. You, of course, have in Praneshacharya a man known all over the south. Let him look into it and tell us what's right in this crisis. He can untangle the delicate strands of right and wrong."(p. 19). He turns over every palm-leaf text and goes through it to the end, but finds no solution that can satisfy his consciousness. He feels afraid to admit that, "the Book of Dharma

had no solution to the present dilemma” (p. 46). The body starts smelling and the next morning the Brahmins of the village gather in the village hall hungry, and reach Praneshacharya's hall and stand with folded hands Garudacharya speaks on behalf of the group, “Our Brahminhood is really in your hands. You must save us from accusations and bad names” (p. 53). At this, Praneshacharya acquaints them with his inability to derive any meaning to the present situation and informs them that he is going to *the Maruti* [Lord Hanuman] temple to find an answer while instructing them. After performing the Holy rituals of worshipping Praneshacharya sits for meditation and presents his conflict in mind, but finally gets no solution, still thinking about the rotting body. As the night falls he gets reminded about the time of his wife’s medicine (p. 62) and when he starts moving towards home, he feels someone’s presence at back and finds Chandri who was waiting secretly for an answer from the *Maruti* temple. As she touches Praneshacharya’s feet as a symbol of gratitude, something happens due to the touch of beasts and they could get up at midnight only. He tells Chandri to inform everyone in the morning gathering about what has happened between them. At the same time, Bramins miserably wait for Praneshacharya in Agrahara, vultures start hovering on Naranappa's home and an unbearable stink spreads around (p. 74). They return home. In the morning the Bramins again gather in Praneshacharya’s home whom he addresses with great difficulty, "I'm lost. I couldn't get *Maruti* to say anything. I know nothing. You do whatever your hearts say” (p. 78). Thereafter, the Brahmins decide to send their wives with children to their parental homes and leave for the monastery in Kaimara where their guru will suggest some way out. Dasacharya dies of fever on the way. Praneshacharya’s wife too dies and he manages her cremation with great difficulty goes to Kaimara and brings four Brahmins for cremation as he is left alone in Agarhara. He was troubled so much that he could not collect the remains of his wife and moved on purposelessly even without a sense of any direction. As the Bramins reached the Monastery, the guru showed his faith in Praneshacharya which again disappointed the Bramins (p. 104). After reaching Agarhara, although they make preparations for the funeral, they wait for Praneshacharya as Garuda says, “Let’s don’t be rash. It’s not right to do anything without Praneshacharya” (p. 111). In this way, one can see that everyone realizes that the body is rotting, but the mass of Brahmins does not dare to cremate the body.

The novelist presents the idea of freewill through the character of Chandri and Naranappa. Both these characters are straightforward, lucid and unambiguous. As Chandri is

concerned she belongs to a family of prostitutes and she has been living with Naranappa as his concubine for ten years (p. 2). It is she who informs Praneshacharya about the demise of her keeper and when the tension arises for his funerals and reaches to expenses, it is she who gives her jewellery to Praneshacharya in the presence of Agarhara Brahmins (p. 10). When she feels grateful for Praneshacharya for his penance or efforts towards finding a way as per the Holy Scriptures or God's grace, she surrenders her body to Praneshacharya and gives him full physical pleasure (p. 63). As Praneshacharya tells her to reveal this intimate experience before the gathering, she does not wish to interrogate his reputation (p. 68). So, after their intimate experience, she hesitates to face Praneshacharya, but she gathers the courage to enter her home where Naranappa's body is lying. As she sees the body, it does not like the person with whom she has been living as the body has swollen up and is reeking (p. 69). Immediately, she goes to the nearby village, requests the cart man, and brings the cart of woods, with his help loads the body and finally cremates in the night before dusk. Then she takes the jewellery that Praneshacharya had returned to her and returns to Kundapura (p. 70).

Naranappa is another character who represents the idea of freewill. He is a Brahmin who interrogates the Brahminical ways openly. The Brahmins of Agarhara did not wish to show their association with him due to his anti-Brahminical actions. He drinks liquor, eats meat, lives with a low-caste woman, Chardri, kills fish, and eats at his Muslim friends. When the Brahmins of Agarhara reach Prajatipura and inform them about the crisis in performing the death rite, the novelist writes:

In the blink of an eye, all the lower-caste Brahmins of Prajatipura gathered on the bund. 'You know-' began Garuda, shrewd man of the world, 'we Agarhara people had a bad fight with Naranappa, we didn't exchange even water and rice. But you here were all his friends, what do you say, now he is dead, his rites have to be done, what do you say?'

The Prajatipura folks were unhappy over their friend's death, but quite happy they were getting a chance to cremate a high caste Brahmin. They were partly pleased because Naranappa ate in their houses with no show of caste pride. (pp. 18-19)

Whatever he thinks and does, speaks with no ambiguity but rather remains lucid. His attitude is not hypocritical like those of Brahmins who start thinking of possessing the gold;

Chandri had given to Praneshacharya for cremation expenses, also cherishing Chandri's body in his heart but does not reveal their feelings. As far as Praneshacharya is concerned, after physical communion with Chandri, though he tells her to reveal before the gathering of Brahmins in the morning, as she does not come back to his home, he heaves a sigh of relief realizing that his dignity will stand integrated. At the same time, he is reminded of Naranappa's words who said while arguing, "You [Pranacharya] read those lush sexy Puranas, but you preach a life of barrenness. But my words, they say what they mean: If I say sleep with a woman, it means sleep with a woman; if I say eat fish, it means eat fish" (p. 25). In this respect, even Praneshacharya becomes a symbol of hypocrisy, whereas Naranappa strongly asserts his individuality for clarity and straightforwardness.

To conclude *Samskara* presents the decaying Brahminism smeared in lust, greed, and hypocrisy in the name of religious supremacy in Hinduism where the most orthodox adherents do not find answers to the basic questions regarding life and death rituals and which further leads to the decadence of their common sense as a result they become incompetent to make rational decisions in their life. For example, Naranappa could not be excommunicated throughout his life (47) and Praneshacharya in an interior monologue says, "I tried to win a victory here over Naranappa. But I was defeated, defeated-fell flat on my face" (p. 100). On the other hand, characters practicing freewill primarily are swayed by their emotions and show the courage to accept them as they are and exhibit more emotional intelligence through their decisive actions as represented by Chandri. Moreover, the characters epitomize freewill and commonsense although via rebelling like Naranappa and Chandri share more happiness for the larger welfare of society than the orthodox religion irrespective of ethics.

Works Cited:

- Abrams, M.H. and Geoffrey Galt Harpham. *A Glossary of Literary Terms*. Cengage Learning India Private Limited, 2018.
- Ananthamurthy, U. R. *Samskara: A Rite for a Dead Man*. Trans. A. K. Ramanujan. Oxford University Press, 1976.

Bary, Peter. *Beginning Theory*. Viva Books Private Limited, 2013.

Bodhale, Anand B., and Rajesh G. Karankal. "Religious dogmatism and moral degeneration in UR Ananthamurthy's *Samskara*: A rite for a dead man." *Journal of Higher Education and Research Society: A Refereed International* Vol. 4, Issue 2, (Oct. 2016), pp. 584-594.

Chitra, S. "Hollowness of Cultural Hegemony in UR Ananthamurthy's *Samskara*." *International Journal of English: Literature, Language and Skills*, Volume 7, Issue 3, October 2018, pp. 23-30.

Cuddon, J.A. *Dictionary of Literary Terms and Literary Theory*. Penguin Books Limited, 1999.

Marasinghe, Sachini. "Cadaverous Images of the Caste System: An Analysis of UR Ananthamurthy's Novella *Samskara* and Mahasweta Devi's Short Story "Douloti the Bountiful"." *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Review*, Vol. 5, No. 3 (2020). pp. 168-178.

Mondal, Arijit. "Pandemic and Superstitions: Anantha Murthy's *Samskara* as a Testimony to Fragile Society." *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, Vol-9, Issue-1, Jan-Feb, 2024, pp.193-203.

Nayar, Pramod K. *Contemporary Literary and Cultural Theory*. Dorling Kindersley (India) Private Limited, 2010.

Nisha, Shwet, and Arzoo Ahmad. "Caste Conundrums: Critiquing Harrowing Hypocrisy in UR Ananthamurthy's *Samskara*: A Rite for a Dead Man." *Anand Bihari*: Vol. 40, Issue 28, 2023, pp. 30-36.

Patel, Rupal S. "Satire in *Samskara* by Anant Murthi". *Research Hub – International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, Vol. 2, Issue 9, (September 2015), pp. 1-4.

Rose, Gladin, and Janaky Sreedharan. "Brahmanical patriarchy: A paradigm of patriarchal power." *Research Journal of English Language and Literature*, Vol. 3, Issue 2 (2015), pp. 190-196.

Roy, Abhinanda. "The portrayal of casteism, orthodoxy and social exclusion in Indian society: a study of Ananthamurthy's Samskara." *Population health and regional development: challenges and issues* (2021), pp. 45-51.

Sharon Pillai. "Back to the Future: Tracking the Moral Imperative in, of, and through *Samskara*." *College Literature*, vol. 41, no. 2, 2014, pp. 97–119. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24544320>. Accessed 30 June 2024.

Sharma, Milan Swaroop. "Rituals in Conflict with Modernization: A Critical Perspective on UR Ananthamurthy's Samskara." *Journal of Literature, Culture & Media Studies*, Vol. IV, Jan. - Dec. 2012, pp. 185-194.

Sharma, Sanjeev Kumar. "The Stream of Indian Culture." *Bharatiya Manyaprad*, Vol. 7, 2019, pp. 112-126.

Sharma, Suruchi. "Hypocrisy and Gender Discourse: A Critical Appraisal of UR Ananthamurthy's Samskara: A Rite for a Dead Man." *The Expression: An International Multidisciplinary e-Journal*, Vol. 4 Issue 4 (August 2018), pp. 28-33.

Shesham, Rajesh Shriniwas. "Thoughts on Modernism in Ananthamurthy's Samskara." *Epitome: International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol. 8, Issue 3 (March 2022), pp. 1-5.

Turnbull, Joanna, et al., editors. *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*. Oxford University Press, 2010.

Williams, Raymond. *Marxism and Literature*. Oxford University Press, 1977.